

NATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION CONSUMPTION IN PUBLIC SERVICES: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

Mansur Yunusov

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Academy of Public Administration under head of the department, PhD, associate professor
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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the national experience in the development of information consumption in public services: problems and solutions, increasing information literacy, problems and achievements of media education, media literacy culture of public servants in public civil service.

Globalization, digitization trends, conflict of political, economic, ideological interests in the world mediapolis increased the informational and psychological impact of the media, intensified the process of struggle for people's consciousness. The rapid flow of information on the information superhighway, the actualization of the problem of digital inequality, information security and cyber security, the increase in the commercial functions of information as a commodity, the pollution of the news environment, the appearance of various inappropriate forms of information in it, the language of hostility and hatred in the process of mass communication, emotional resonance, information blockade, media the expansion of addiction, fake information and manipulative influence, in order to ensure the priority of national interests and state security, in-depth research into the consumption of media products by the population, regulation of the information world in the public mind using media education tools, preservation of information and digital health, development of new methods of dealing with information, , in particular, requires the formation of information culture of young people.

In the developed countries of the world, efforts in this regard began in the last century, and today in many countries, media education has become a mandatory, permanent component of general education. Development of media education, formation of information literacy of children, teenagers and young people and ensuring their safety in the online environment are on the agenda in Uzbekistan. From this point of view, there is a need to study the real situation in the modern media space, the history of the emergence of media education and the stages of formation, scientific-theoretical, practical, methodological bases and concepts, advanced foreign experience in the context of information-psychological struggles. At the same time, it is of urgent importance to create the "Uzbek model" of media education, based on the idea of national independence through scientific research, taking into account

the peculiarities of the national education system, mentality, eastern historical and spiritual foundations, without directly copying the experience of foreign countries.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoev, in his greeting to the press and media workers on June 26, 2021, said, "Today, generations, creative schools, traditions, concepts and imaginations are being renewed. The Internet age is pushing its own requirements and rules. In such a complex period of transition, we should recognize that our national journalism is facing various trials and difficulties that have not been seen before and we should think about overcoming them together. In the new Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to modernization of the country and liberalization of all spheres of life, openness and transparency of activities of state authorities and management bodies, ensuring freedom of speech, introduction of digital economy. In this sense, this study aims to prevent the spread of false information by providing unbiased information in the mass media and social networks, as well as the freedom of citizens to receive and distribute information, as defined in goals 71 and 89 of the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026". It was carried out within the framework of the implementation of priority tasks related to the further strengthening of the rights of citizens, the improvement of the culture of citizens' use of information and communication tools, the prevention of violations of the right to privacy related to the disclosure of personal and confidential information on the Internet, and the creation of a system for the prevention of cybercrime.

Of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On protection of children from information harmful to their health", "On cyber security", "On keeping state secrets", "On personal information", "On trade secrets", "On advertising", "On information provision", " On the principles and guarantees of freedom of information", "On the openness of the activities of state authorities and management bodies", the laws of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 "On the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for the period 2022-2026", May 5, 2020 No. PF-6079 dated October "On approval of the strategy of Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" and measures for its effective implementation, No. PF-5653 dated February 2, 2019 "On additional measures related to the further development of the information sector and mass communications" and Cabinet of Ministers No. 707 dated September 5, 2018 "Information security on the global Internet This dissertation research serves to a certain extent in the implementation of the tasks defined in the decision "On measures for further improvement of

There are text-centered, structural, territorial (market), technological, and ecological approaches in the studies aimed at the theoretical study of the media space, and in each of them, the issue of interpretation and influence on the consciousness of people in the media is expressed. According to the geopolitical approach, the information war in the media space is an inter-state conflict, according to the supporters of the psychological approach, the essence of the information war is to covertly influence people's minds through information, in the communicative direction, the information war is a communication technology in which intelligence, political and psychological actions of the opposite parties are carried out. interpreted as, according to the conflictological approach, it is shown that conflicts in the information war are not only interstate, but also group, interpersonal, military and political phenomena.

Information-psychological, cyber wars organization forms have been clarified. In the information struggle, the discrediting of each other, the spread of information serving their own interests, the increase in one-sided and false information, the impact of such information on people and society is considered in political, economic, cultural, spiritual, and physical directions. The inevitability of conflict in a polarized world requires reliance on media education to minimize the negative impact of the media, which is becoming a weapon of struggle, to prevent the abuse of freedom of speech and opinion, to receive and distribute information, to create a healthy information environment, and to counter disinformation.

Theoretically, the monological nature of mass media and the collective authorship of a media product ensure its universality and neutrality. However, the individual acceptance of it by audience members, different interpretations, the presence of mass media that do not adhere to law and moral standards, universal principles, or information disseminating channels that do not have the status of mass media, increase the relevance of information culture.

In the case of Uzbekistan, the need to introduce media education is primarily based on the abundance of information, the presence of false and harmful information, news and cyber risks. P. McGinnis' views on the characteristics of the FOMO sapiens generation, as well as the theoretical foundations of media addiction by X. Zhang and Z. Zhong¹, T.T.Thomas et al.'s influence of phubbing on personal life², The induction of alienation by X. Wu et al³, Ł.Tomczyk, and E.S.Lizde's effects of nomophobia (fear of being without a phone) on family well-being⁴ in his dedicated studies, attention is paid to the problems of information consumption, mental state in communication and impact on social life.

Sources that reflect the classical views of the general theoretical foundations of media education are based on the views of L. Masterman, C. Bazalgette, D. Buckingham, K. Tyner, A. V. Fedorov, modern case studies that investigate an attribute, component, problem of media education S. J. Paxton, Y. F. Luo , I.Celik and others will be covered. Based on this, the scientific resources related to media education are classified into such types as those related to the development and experience of media education in a country, related to the development of media education in a certain period (with a historical approach), scientific resources about the person who contributed to the development of media education, his works, and his scientific school.

By analyzing ancient sources, rare works of scholars in the context of media education, the eastern historical-spiritual foundations of the concepts of news literacy, media literacy, fact-checking, which are considered as neologisms today, and historical manifestations of information evaluation have been found. For example, in one of the ancient sources, "Avesta", lying is condemned as a sin, it is considered as betrayal of the true faith. It states "Truth is the

¹ Zhang, X., & Zhong, Z. J. (2020). Extending media system dependency theory to informational media use and environmentalism: A cross-national study. *Telematics and Informatics*, 50, 101378. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TELE.2020.101378>

² Thomas, T. T., Carnelley, K. B., & Hart, C. M. (2022). Phubbing in romantic relationships and retaliation: A daily diary study. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 137, 107398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHB.2022.107398>

³ Wu, X., Zhang, L., Yang, R., Zhu, T., Xiang, M., & Wu, G. (2022). Parents can't see me, can peers see me? Parental phubbing and adolescents' peer alienation via the mediating role of parental rejection. *Child Abuse & Neglect*, 132, 105806. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHIABU.2022.105806>

⁴ Tomczyk, Ł., & Lizde, E. S. (2022). Nomophobia and Phubbing: Wellbeing and new media education in the family among adolescents in Bosnia and Herzegovina. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 137, 106489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHILDYOUTH.2022.106489>

best gift...", "Truth is the best gift...". Yasht's final prayers ended with these sentences, which were repeated ten times: "Kulfat may come to him, if he despises the truth", "He does not fly to deceptions, he does not follow lies", "Lies without faith", "Those who do not go beyond words, cannot get help from Him. Sentences such as "A liar is deprived of happiness, devoid of virtues" and "Wanders in a false pasture" show the value and importance of the truth, and express the sharp intolerance of deception and lies.

The great scientist and thinker Abu Rayhan Beruni (973-1048) shows the difference between the reality seen by the eyes and the message conveyed by someone else, that is, reality and representation in the work "India". "The words of the person who says that the message is not what the eye sees is very true. Because seeing consists in the sight of the visible thing when it is present and standing in its place. If the message had not been laced with falsehoods, it would have been more prominent than seen. Because the moment of seeing and looking is limited to a piece of time. And the message indicates the state of the thing that has passed before and will come after the time that is visible to [the watcher]; that's why the news informs about the things that exist and the things that don't exist. Writing is one of the types of communication that can be considered more honorable than other types; if there were no eternal traces of the pen, would we know the messages of the nations properly? Then the message given about what might normally be is equally [indifferently] true and false; whistleblowers take on the color of truth and falsehood. Because people's goals are different, there is a lot of strife and strife between peoples. The conflict of interests, the connection of the information distribution with the human factor, causes the interpretation of different interpretations, and the emergence of false information. A great thinker warns against lies. This is the very principle that representation in media education cannot replace reality, it can correspond to reality or deny it. Yusuf Khos Hajib's "Kutadgu Bilig", Kaikovus's "Nightmare", Jalaluddin Rumi's "Ichindagi Ichindadir", Amir Temur's "Tuzuklari Temur", Mirzo Ulughbek's "The History of Four Nations", Alisher Navoi's "Khamsa", Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's "Boburnoma" are also works. will be analyzed from the point of view of information literacy and fact-checking. Such examples can be used as a didactic basis for the integrated introduction of media education to subjects such as history and literature.

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